

Legal aspects of occupational health: An approach to the procedure and patrimonial responsibility in Colombia

Aspectos legales de salud laboral: Un acercamiento al procedimiento y la responsabilidad patrimonial en Colombia

Aspectos legais da saúde ocupacional: Uma abordagem do procedimento e da responsabilidade patrimonial na Colômbia

Jorge Mario Posada López¹, Carlos Alberto Severiche Sierra²

Recibido:10/08/2022 Aceptado:15/11/2022 Publicado:20//12/2022

ABSTRACT

The delay in establishing regulations for worker safety was largely due to the existing production systems, based on the exploitation of cheap labor and a very precarious mechanization of processes. And this together with a restricted political vision about the role of workers, their rights and duties. A review was made of the research on the significance of the legal aspects of occupational health: an approach to the procedure and patrimonial responsibility. The main purpose of this review article is to qualitatively analyze the scientific literature available in the Scielo, Redalyc, Dialnet databases and official websites, using as search words: occupational health; Industrial Security; labor legislation, patrimonial responsibility. Pertinent information related to the proposed objective was obtained, which is presented in 3 sections: Legal Framework; Patrimonial Liability; Procedure. It is necessary to implement a security plan in light of current regulations, this can be operated in conjunction with other cooperatives, the union with the academic sector and the support of the state's health entities, thus establishing cooperative work with benefit. to all spin-off-style sectors.

Keywords: Labor legislation, Occupational health, Industrial safety, Property liability.

RESUMEN

El retraso en el establecimiento de normatividad en pro de la seguridad de los trabajadores se debió en gran medida a los sistemas de producción existentes, basados en la explotación de mano de obra barata y en una muy precaria mecanización de los procesos. Y esto unido a una visión política restringida acerca del papel de los trabajadores, sus derechos y deberes. Se hizo una revisión sobre las investigaciones acerca de la trascendencia de los aspectos legales de salud laboral: un acercamiento al procedimiento y la responsabilidad patrimonial. El presente artículo de revisión tiene

¹Corporación Universitaria Minuto de Dios – UNIMINUTO. Barranquilla, Colombia. jorge.posada@uniminuto.edu.co -<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9129-8775>

²Corporación Universitaria Minuto de Dios – UNIMINUTO. Barranquilla, Colombia. carlos.severiche@uniminuto.edu.co -<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7190-4849>

como principal analizar cualitativamente la literatura científica disponible en las bases de datos Scielo, Redalyc, Dialnet y páginas Web oficiales, empleando como palabras de búsqueda: salud laboral; seguridad industrial; legislación laboral, responsabilidad patrimonial. Se obtuvo información pertinente relacionada con el objetivo propuesto, la cual se presenta en 3 secciones: Marco Legal; Responsabilidad Patrimonial; Procedimiento. Es necesario implementar un plan de seguridad a la luz de la normatividad vigente, este se puede operar en conjunto con otras cooperativas, la unión con el sector académico y el respaldo de las entidades de salud del estado, estableciendo así, un trabajo cooperativo con beneficio a todos los sectores estilo spin-offs.

Palabras Clave: Legislación laboral, Salud laboral, Seguridad industrial, Responsabilidad patrimonial.

RESUMO

O atraso no estabelecimento de regulamentos para a segurança dos trabalhadores deveu-se em grande parte aos sistemas de produção existentes, baseados na exploração de mão-de-obra barata e numa mecanização muito fraca dos processos. E isto aliado a uma visão política restrita sobre o papel dos trabalhadores, os seus direitos e deveres. Foi feita uma revisão da pesquisa sobre o significado dos aspectos jurídicos da saúde ocupacional: uma abordagem do procedimento e da responsabilidade patrimonial. O objetivo principal deste artigo de revisão é analisar qualitativamente a produção científica disponível nas bases de dados Scielo, Redalyc, Dialnet e sites oficiais, utilizando como palavras de busca: saúde ocupacional; segurança industrial; legislação trabalhista, responsabilidade patrimonial. Foram obtidas informações pertinentes relacionadas ao objetivo proposto, as quais são apresentadas em 3 seções: Marco Legal; Responsabilidade Patrimonial; Procedimento. É necessária a implementação de um plano de segurança à luz da regulamentação vigente, este pode ser operado em conjunto com outras cooperativas, a união com o setor acadêmico e o apoio das entidades estaduais de saúde, estabelecendo assim um trabalho cooperativo com benefício para todos os spin- setores fora de estilo.

Palavras-chave: Legislação trabalhista, Saúde ocupacional, Segurança industrial, Responsabilidade patrimonial.

INTRODUCTION

The concepts linked to the protection of the worker against occupational dangers and risks and the corresponding legislation were aspects practically unknown in Colombia until the beginning of the 20th century. In 1904, Rafael Uribe Uribe specifically addressed the issue of safety at work in what later became Law 57 of 1915 known as the “Uribe law” on occupational accidents and occupational diseases and which became the first law related to the issue of occupational health in the country (Quintana et al., 2020; Diaz et al., 2017).

The delay in establishing regulations for worker safety was largely due to the existing production systems, based on the exploitation of cheap labor and a very poor mechanization of

processes. And this together with a restricted political vision about the role of workers, their rights and duties (Bedoya et al., 20). This law was followed by others that sought to strengthen the protection of workers against the dangers and risks of their work. and that had significance in the future of occupational health in Colombia: Law 46 of 1918, which dictated Hygiene and Health measures for employees and employers, Law 37 of 1921, which established collective life insurance for employees, the Law 10 of 1934 (Valero & Riaño, 2020).

Where occupational illness, unemployment benefits, vacations and employment contracts were regulated, Law 96 of 1938, creation of the entity today known as the Ministry of Social Protection, Law 44 of 1939, creation of Mandatory Insurance and compensation for work accidents. work and Decree 2350 of 1944, which promulgated the foundations of the Substantive Labor Code and the obligation to protect workers in their work (Mora, 2016).

But it was in 1945 when the foundations of occupational health in Colombia were cemented, when Law 6 (General Labor Law) was approved, by which provisions relating to labor conventions, professional associations, collective conflicts and jurisdiction were promulgated. especially work matters. Some amendments were made to this law with decrees 1600 and 1848 of 1951. The following years were one of great movement in the field of occupational health in Colombia, because in 1946 with Law 90 the Social Security Institute was created, with the objective of providing health and pension services to Colombian workers (Osorio, 2021).

In 1948, through Legislative Act No.77, the National Office of Industrial Medicine and Hygiene was created and later, with Decree 3767 of 1949, industrial safety and hygiene policies were established for work establishments. These structures emerged as compensation for a situation of helplessness of workers by private and public companies (Lizarazo et al., 2011).

Through Law 100 of 1993 and Decree Law 1295 of 1994, the System was created General of Professional Risks, which established an insurance model deprived of occupational risks and whose main objective was the creation and promotion of a culture of prevention of work accidents and illnesses professionals. Before this law came into force, there was a system focused on damage repair rather than prevention, so that emphasis was placed on medical care models (that is, diagnosis and treatment), disability pensions, and compensation, among others (Bravo, 2019).

These functions were provided by the Social Security Institute (ISS), a state entity, the only body authorized for these services. Under the new system, the Professional Risk Administrators (ARP) were created, which are responsible for carrying out prevention, advice and evaluation of professional risks, as well as the provision of health services and payment of economic benefits to their members (García, 2008).

Medical care is usually subcontracted to health service providing institutions (IPS) which, together with health promotion entities (EPS), are, in some cases, business units of the same entity. In general, the Colombian state has made great efforts to implement strategies through the legal provisions contained in the General System of Professional Risks to proactively protect workers against the risks of diseases or accidents and at the same time prevent the negative effects that arise. can be generated by this type of events on the physical and mental health of workers (Torres et al., 2012).

However, it is still necessary to reinforce the requirement for compliance with the rules, starting with affiliation to the system, which does not exceed 30% of the coverage of the economically active population, and resolve the false employment-protection against risks dilemma. labor. Given that in Colombia the unemployment rate has remained around 12%⁵ in recent years, it is only natural that priority be given to the creation and sustainability of employment, rather than to improving the quality of working life through better employment systems. control and protection of occupational risks (Moreno, 2023).

LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The legal framework provides us with the bases on which institutions build and determine the scope and nature of political participation. The legal framework of an election, and especially issues related to its integrity, are often found in a number of interrelated regulatory provisions and laws.

The pension scheme is composed of the Solidarity Medium Premium Regime with Defined Benefit and the Individual Savings Regime with Solidarity. It is one through which members or their beneficiaries obtain an old-age, disability or survivors' pension, or compensation, previously defined (Posada et al., 2023, Duque & Duque, 2016).

According to Law 1438 of 2011, Primary Health Care (PHC) is the intersectoral coordination strategy that allows comprehensive and integrated care, from public health, health promotion, disease prevention, diagnosis, treatment, the rehabilitation of the patient at all levels of complexity, in order to guarantee a higher level of well-being in the users, without prejudice to the legal powers of each of the actors of the General System of Social Security in Health (Franco, 2015).

PHC in Colombia, according to Betancurth et al. (2022):

- It is a strategy that contemplates three integrated and interdependent components: intersectoral/transsectoral action for health, social, community and citizen participation, and health services.
- It adjusts to the political, economic and social context of the country.
- It is focused on individuals, families and communities.
- It is aimed at establishing conditions for materializing the effective enjoyment of the right to health and the reduction of inequalities, through comprehensive health care from a perspective of social and economic determinants,
- It is not only a sectoral provision of health services, but the coordinated action of the State, institutions and society for the improvement of health and the creation of a healthy and healthy environment.
- Emphasizes health promotion.

Occupational Risks are Work Accidents and Occupational Diseases. Law 1562 of 2012, defines the General Occupational Risk System, as the set of public and private entities, standards and procedures, designed to prevent, protect and care for workers from the effects of diseases and accidents that may occur to them. occasion or as a consequence of the work they carry out (Álvarez et al., 2018).

Decree Law 4107 of 2011 determines, among other functions of the Ministry of Health and Social Protection, that of formulating policy, directing, guiding, adopting and evaluating the execution of plans, programs and projects of the National Government in matters of public health and risks. labor, as well as promoting the articulation of the actions of the State, society, the family, the individual and the other people responsible for the execution of the occupational risk activities carried out by the Ministry, activities that, among others, correspond to the insurance or affiliation to the General Occupational Risk System; with Human Talent in Safety and Health at Work; and with public health, in terms of protecting the health of the country's working population (Severiche et al., 2021).

In Resolution 1841 of 2013, Health and the Workplace as a dimension within the framework of the Ten-Year Public Health Plan, is defined as the set of sectoral and trans-sectoral policies and interventions that seek the well-being and protection of the health of workers, to through the promotion of healthy ways, conditions and lifestyles in the workplace, the maintenance of the physical, mental and social well-being of people in all occupations, and the promotion of interventions that positively modify the situations and conditions of interest for the health of workers in the formal and informal sectors of the economy (Severiche et al., 2023a).

PATRIMONIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Responsibility is defined by Cortés (2002) as the “obligation to repair the damage caused, deducing from it, therefore, that, if there is no damage, there is no responsibility.” Now, given that in any employment relationship there are two parties, the employer and the workers, the responsibilities of both must be distinguished.

Firstly, from the employer, they derive precisely from his power to indicate to the worker the way, time and place to carry out the work and his power to sanction anyone who does not do it in the indicated manner. Consequently, if he has these powers, he must also be responsible for the risks that may arise in the production process and especially those that affect the safety and health of workers (Gómez et al., 2020). Second, the responsibility of workers derives from failure to fulfill their obligations as a worker. Therefore, it is their obligation to observe the legal and regulatory measures of industrial safety and hygiene that are adopted, as well as to follow the training on safety and hygiene provided by the employer (Ahumada et al., 2022; Guillén & Guillén, 2017).

Safety and hygiene have become priority issues in the European Union by virtue of relative positions or social policies and the internal market. Many professionals will have to face the numerous issues that will arise regarding occupational risk prevention in the performance of their activities without having received specific training in this matter (Henao, 2017). Therefore, the need for this training is no longer exclusive to those who are going to perform prevention functions in companies, but there are greater demands and responsibilities, they must reach all elements of the company and especially the technicians involved. on the production line (Severiche et al., 2023b).

Industrial hygiene within companies is of great importance because many industrial processes and operations produce or use compounds that can be harmful to the health of workers.

It is a science and art dedicated to the anticipation, recognition, evaluation and control of those environmental stressors or elements that arise in the workplace, which can cause illness, deterioration in health, and important well-being among workers (Márquez et al., 2016).

For this reason, within organizations it is important to have an industrial hygienist, who will ensure the prevention, evaluation and control of different incidents, as well as the application of laws that aim to provide workers with safe and stable conditions. Industrial hygiene and safety at work is a fundamental element in order to ensure that the principles in which it is stated and become part of their daily work or activity, so that the working conditions are known and taken into account from the design and implementation phase of the project (Quintana et al., 2021; Céspedes & Martínez, 2016).

Hygiene and Safety at work should be one of the key points of any organization. It is part of your social responsibility to take care of your employees, protecting them from risks and ensuring a healthy environment. Among the needs that the employer must satisfy during a worker's working life are the needs for physical and emotional security (Alarcón et al., 2017).

The law requires employers to provide working conditions that do not physically or morally harm their employees. For this reason, companies must pay special attention to three aspects that have an important impact on the issue: compliance with legislation, safety of their personnel and care for the environment. Regarding safety in the workplace, the role is played by the staff (Neves, 2020).

For this reason, it is necessary that a “safety and risk prevention culture” be transmitted throughout the company, which leads to achieving high levels of productivity and consequent efficiency in its total management. A Hygiene and Safety program must be conceived as part of the company, and not as something that must be carried out additionally. This program is a set of activities that allow workers and the company to be kept with the least possible exposure to the dangers of the work environment (Arango et al., 2013).

The costs related to sick leave, disability retirement, and replacement of injured or dead employees are much greater than those allocated to maintaining a Health and Safety program. Furthermore, the risks and illnesses that can be attributed to work can have very negative effects on the morale of employees, creating demotivation and dissatisfaction. The Human Resources department is responsible for coordinating communication and security training programs (Benavides, 2023).

But its success will depend on the action of the Directors and Supervisors, as well as the conduct that the employees consequently adopt. Security is a Staff function, but its compliance is the responsibility of Line. Internalizing the value of Hygiene and Safety at work depends on a systematic task, where policies and procedures are reinforced every day. That is why the commitment must begin at high-level management, who must be aware of the priority place that this issue deserves (Lizarazo, 2011).

Senior management can demonstrate its commitment through different actions such as: personal and routine interest in safety activities, giving it great importance in company meetings, providing those responsible for its planning with the necessary resources, ensuring that the work

environment The organization is adequate, including the topic of safety in the training. Without this commitment, any attempt to reduce unsafe acts by workers will have little result (Albujar et al., 2022).

The First Line Supervisor is a key link in the chain. Their work is especially important in the induction of new staff. This must consist of a detailed explanation of everything the worker must do, including the dangers of the area, the safety measures and the procedure to follow in case of risks or incidents (Zapata et al., 2017).

The criterion for induction into the position is applied in exactly the same way to that person who has been transferred, and who, regardless of how long he or she has been within the organization, is as new as the person who has just joined. It is important to keep in mind that experience greatly reduces risks, and training in many cases can replace experience, which is why safety training can substantially reduce risks (Santana et al., 2023).

The Supervisor must fulfill an educational role, transmitting the guidelines clearly and encouraging employees to follow the stipulated procedures. The key to keeping risks at a low level is “prevention.” One of the aspects that make this up is the existence of procedures. These allow people to know what the prevention, protection and security measures are, so that the risks of each operation are minimal. The key to prevention is “preventive observation”, which allows us to focus on not only what is wrong, but also on all the consequences that this can bring (Serna et al., 2020).

PROCEDURE

Recognize, evaluate and control the possibilities of damage to the health of workers in the development of their activities. In addition, establishing associations between the risk of exposure and health effects and integrating an action plan that will contain suggestions and guidelines for improving the work environment, for better control of health risks; For this reason, the exposure of workers to the maximum and minimum average concentrations of aromatic solvents in the work area must be quantitatively estimated (Matabanchoy, 2012).

Prevent occupational risks which occur as a consequence of production activities; therefore, production that does not take into account safety and hygiene measures is not good production. Good production must satisfy the necessary conditions of the three essential elements, which are safety, productivity and quality of the products, otherwise they contribute to the reduction of their partners and customers (Pulido et al., 2020).

When we talk about diagnosis, we refer to the identification of the problems that occur, based on a thorough study. To do this, it is necessary to follow a series of steps as proposed by Manso (2014), which allows a description of the process through which the objectives and methods are established to evaluate and assess the necessary actions subsequently.

In such a way, it begins with a Diagnosis of the situation, which aims to use accident statistics, management audits, hazard identification, risk evaluation, risk maps, job evaluation methods, among others. . From this, the objectives are defined, since the starting situation is already known (Diaz & Muñoz, 2013).

Risk prevention includes the systematized analysis of each job, determining its characteristics, its objectives, the way it is carried out and the standards that must be observed when carrying it out. In such a way, since the risk is a consequence of a poor functional situation of the system, the causes must be identified, and then influence them through preventive measures that allow: preventing the disturbance of the elements, improving safety in the operation of the system. and improve their interrelation (Díaz, 2018).

In this sense, the starting point for risk prevention must be the creation and maintenance of interest in safety, at all levels of the organization. Risk is the creation or materialization of a risk in an unforeseen event, which interrupts or interferes with the continuity of work, which may cause damage to people or property (Bracho & Quintero, 2020).

In relation to work spaces, the work environment is defined and limited in the Organic Law of Prevention, Conditions and Work Environment of 1986: Article 5.- Work environment is understood, for the purposes of this Law: 1. Places, premises or sites, closed or outdoors, where people linked by an employment relationship provide services to companies, offices, farms, industrial, agricultural and special establishments of any nature, public or private, with the exceptions established by this Law. The socio-cultural and physical infrastructure circumstances that immediately surround the man-work relationship, conditioning the quality of life of workers and their families (Álvarez et al., 2016).

In fact, every work activity, depending on its object, is exposed to risks. In that sense, the doctrine has developed various classifications to discriminate them, and it is this element that forces the employer to establish certain conditions that must prevail in the workplace. work environment, to minimize such risks and thus guarantee health (Acosta et al., 2015).

The socio-cultural situations, work organization and physical infrastructure that immediately surround the relationship between men and women and work, conditioning the quality of life of workers and their families (Severiche et al., 2023c). The air, aquatic and terrestrial spaces located around the company, work center, exploitation, work, establishment; as well as other community associative forms of a productive or service nature and that are part of them (Madrid, 2014).

In order to integrate each of the parts that constitute an organization, Security programs can be designed to achieve their purposes in two main ways, the first approach is to create an environment and psychological aptitudes that promote security, because the risks can be reduced when workers consciously think about safety; The second approach is the development and maintenance of a safe environment for physical work (Díaz & Rentería, 2017).

The organizational leader must use strategies to get to know his staff and foster an environment that facilitates their effective performance. Fulfill the corresponding functions based on the interrelationship with their subordinates and supervisors, in a team, harmonious and communicative environment; which allows you to know the various sensitivities of the workers, not with the purpose of delving into their lives but rather detecting the attitudes that can negatively and positively influence the company, in order to combat the former and enhance the latter (Grueso, 2016). As well as, stimulate people's commitment to the institution and cultivate a

work environment based on the quality of work life and harmonious interrelation in the organizational climate; A good organizational climate is a necessary condition in the quality management model (Arrieta et al., 2026).

CONCLUSION

Its employees must be affiliated with the occupational risk system in force in the country, in this way they comply with associated regulations and, above all, prevent accidents and occupational diseases, in the same way strengthen the relationship with occupational risk insurers and implement a disclosure plan. and monitoring with constant visits to the collection centers by them seeking promotion and prevention in terms of occupational health. By taking into account the opinion of all employees, these clear relationships make it easier for managers to supervise lower levels of the organization. It is necessary to implement a security plan in light of current regulations, this can be operated in conjunction with other cooperatives, the union with the academic sector and the support of the state's health entities, thus establishing cooperative work with benefit. to all spin-off-style sectors.

REFERENCES

- Acosta Plaza, B. E., Lasso Quintero, M. I., & Pulido Fierro, D. P. (2015). Condiciones del entorno físico del trabajo y su relación con el estrés en empleados públicos del sector educativo en algunas instituciones colombianas.
- Ahumada, I., Palacio, J., Severiche, C., Guzmán, A., Castellón, L. (2022). Investigación Formativa en Seguridad y Salud en el Trabajo: Oportunidades y Retos desde el Caribe Colombiano. Fondo Editorial de la Universidad Nacional Experimental Sur del Lago Jesús María Semprúm (UNESUR), 1-157.
- Alarcón, J. A. O., López, J. R. R., & Palma, H. G. H. (2017). Importancia de la seguridad de los trabajadores en el cumplimiento de procesos, procedimientos y funciones. *Academia & Derecho*, (14), 155-175.
- Albújar Verona, C, Celis Castillo, D, Rojas Sánchez, Es, & Medina-Cardozo, I. (2022). Digital platforms and indicators in the occupational safety and health management system: a systematic review. *DYNA*, 89(224), 165-172.
- Álvarez Torres, S & Riaño-Casallas, M. (2018). La política pública de seguridad y salud en el trabajo: el caso colombiano. *Revista Gerencia y Políticas de Salud*, 17(35), 1-56.
- Arango-Soler, J. M., Luna-García, J. E., Correa-Moreno, Y. A., & Campos, A. C. (2013). Marco legal de los riesgos profesionales y la salud ocupacional en Colombia, Siglo XX. *Revista de Salud Pública*, 15(3), 354-365.
- Arrieta, A. P., Gómez, A. R., Corrales, L. V., & Araujo, E. S. (2016). Calidad de servicios para optimizar la atención en el centro de diagnóstico cardiovascular del magdalena-Colombia. *Desarrollo Gerencial*, 8(2), 161-185.
- Bedoya, E., Behaine, B., Gomez, E., Burgos, Y., Carrillo, M., Severiche, C., & Torres, J. I. (2018). Control de pérdidas por accidentalidad laboral en el sector logístico. *Revista Espacios*, 39(09).
- Benavides, L. K. C. (2023). Exposición a radiaciones ionizantes en el personal de la salud, efectos y normatividad en Colombia. *Gestión de la seguridad y la salud en el trabajo*, 5(1 (6)), 89-92.

- Betancurth-Loaiza, D, Vélez-Álvarez, C, Sánchez-Palacio, N, & Jaramillo-Ángel, Claudia P. (2022). Atención primaria social en Colombia: una mirada desde una experiencia exitosa. *Revista de la Universidad Industrial de Santander. Salud*, 54, e332.
- Bracho-Paz, D. C., & Quintero-Medina, J. L. (2020). La fatiga laboral en el ámbito de seguridad y salud laboral en el marco jurídico venezolano. *Cienciamatria*, 6(1), 237-263.
- Bravo, G. E. P. (2019). La responsabilidad plena de perjuicios y el sistema general de riesgos laborales. Precedente judicial de la Corte Suprema de Justicia 2019. *Revista Ibero-Latinoamericana de Seguros*, 28(50), 177-205.
- Céspedes Socarrás, G, & Martínez Cumbreira, J. (2016). Un análisis de la seguridad y salud en el trabajo en el sistema empresarial cubano. *Revista latinoamericana de derecho social*.
- Díaz Bambula, F., & Rentería Pérez, E. (2017). De la seguridad al riesgo psicosocial en el trabajo en la legislación colombiana de salud ocupacional. *Estudios Socio-Jurídicos*, 19(2), 129-155.
- Díaz, J. M. C. (2018). Técnicas de prevención de riesgos laborales. Editorial Tebar.
- Díaz, O, & Muñoz Maya, C. (2013). Aplicación de la GTC 34 y GTC 45 en una S.A.S. de servicios en HSEQ: estudio de caso. *Suma de Negocios*, 4(1), 71-87.
- Franco-Giraldo A. El rol de los profesionales de la salud en la atención primaria en salud (APS). *Rev. Fac. Nac. Salud Pública* 2015; 33(3): 414-424.
- Garavito Hernández, Y., Daza Ríos, C. T. ., & Ramírez Torres, W. E. . (2023). Cultura organizacional y cultura de seguridad: una revisión de la literatura. *Revista Colombiana De Salud Ocupacional*, 12(2), e-8622.
- García, A. (2008). El Sistema General De Riesgos Profesionales Vigente En Colombia - Una Visión Interna Y Desde La Decisión 584, Instrumento Andino De Seguridad Y Salud En El Trabajo. *International Law*, (13), 216-253.
- Gil, S & Reyes, L. F. (2022). Estrategias educativas para disminuir los índices de accidentalidad en el tráfico laboral en Colombia. *Revista Colombiana De Salud Ocupacional*, 12(1), e-7887.
- Gómez, E. M., Cogollo, Z., & Severiche, C. A. (2020). Responsabilidad patrimonial frente a la salud laboral en cooperativas de recicladores del Caribe Colombiano. *Revista Espacios*. 798, 1015.
- Grueso, M. P. (Ed.). (2016). Organizaciones saludables y procesos organizacionales e individuales: Comprensión y retos. Editorial Universidad del Rosario
- Guerrero, M. T. V., García, L. M. C., González, Á. A. L., & García, M. J. T. (2024). Recomendaciones para la vigilancia de la salud de los trabajadores con alergias laborales. Una revisión desde la legislación española en prevención de riesgos laborales. *Revista Cubana de Salud y Trabajo*, 13(1), 64-70.
- Guillén, C. M., & Guillén, C. M. (2017, July). El trabajador como sujeto infractor en materia de prevención de riesgos laborales. In *Anales de derecho* (Vol. 35, No. 1).
- Henao, F. (2017). Diagnóstico integral de las condiciones de trabajo y salud. Ecoe ediciones.
- Lizarazo C, Fajardo J, Berrio S, Quintana L. Breve historia de la salud ocupacional en Colombia. *Arch Prev Riesgos Labor* 2011; 14:38-42.
- López-Laverde, J., Salazar, L. G., & López, T. T. (2023). Representaciones sociales sobre seguridad y salud en el trabajo en universitarios. *Fisioterapia*, 45(2), 92-98.

- Madrid, T. P. L. (2014). Gestión de la seguridad y la salud en el trabajo durante la construcción de obras de infraestructura vial en los departamentos de Atlántico, Magdalena y Bolívar. *SIGNOS-Investigación en sistemas de gestión*, 6(1), 49-57.
- Márquez, K, Ortiz, R, Márquez, O, & Márquez, J. (2016). Aspectos de la higiene y seguridad industrial en el área de reducción de una planta de aluminio en Venezuela. *Universidad, Ciencia y Tecnología*, 20(78), 15-34.
- Matabanchoy Tulcán, S. (2012). Salud En El Trabajo. *Universidad y Salud*, 14(1), 87-102.
- Mora Toscano, Ó. (2016). La reforma laboral implementada durante el segundo gobierno de Alfonso López Pumarejo. *Apuntes del Cenes*, 35(61), 115-146.
- Moreira, J. A. M., & Moreira, J. D. R. M. (2023). Aspectos legales de la prevención de riesgos laborales: Artículo de Revisión. *Ciencia Ecuador*, 5(21), 1-10.
- Neves, J. (2020). Introducción al derecho del trabajo. Fondo Editorial de la PUCP.
- Osorio-Vasco, J. (2021). Panorama de la seguridad y salud en el trabajo de microempresas colombianas ubicadas en un barrio del Municipio de Itagüí, Antioquia, Colombia. *Cadernos de Saúde Pública*, 37, e00175320.
- Posada, J. M., Muñoz Rojas, D., & Severiche Sierra, C. A. (2023). percepción de la calidad de vida en el trabajo por guardias de seguridad privada en el periodo de pandemia COVID-19. *Revista Tajamar*, 2(1), 71-94.
- Pulido-Rojano, ARuiz-Lázaro, A, Ortiz-Ospino, L. (2020). Mejora de procesos de producción a través de la gestión de riesgos y herramientas estadísticas. *Ingeniare. Revista chilena de ingeniería*, 28(1), 56-67.
- Quintana, Á., Bocanegra, V. C., Vega, C. Z., Moreno, A. G., & Severiche, C. (2021). Calidad de vida laboral en operarios de mantenimiento mecánico automotriz. *Ingeniare*, (31), 93-102.
- Quintana, A., Vargas-Ortiz, L., Severiche-Sierra, C., Castro-Bocanegra, V., García-Moreno, A., Vidal-Tovar, C., & Muñoz-Rojas, D. (2020). Knowledge and Attitudes of Health Workers for the Care of Patients COVID-19 in some cities of the Colombian Caribbean. *Indian J Public Health Res Dev*, 11, 219-224.
- Rada Luna, R. J. (2023). Percepción que tienen los trabajadores rurales respecto a la seguridad y salud en el trabajo. *Revista Colombiana De Salud Ocupacional*, 12(1), e-6090.
- Santana Londoño, M, Mondragón Duarte, S, Restrepo Montoya, C, & Flórez Guzmán, M. (2023). Implementación Del Sistema De Gestión De La Seguridad Y Salud En El Trabajo SG-SST. *Revista republicana*, (34), 209-224.
- Serna Ortiz, E. A., Redondo Silvera, P. A., & Cabrera Palacio, R. D. (2020). Trabajo decente y salud ocupacional en las alcaldías del departamento de La Guajira.
- Severiche, C. A., Jiménez Bolívar, F. A., De la Hoz Toscano, M. J., Vidal Tovar, C. R., & Angulo Blanquicett, G. (2023a). Seguridad Y Salud En El Trabajo: Aportes Multidisciplinarios. *Repositorio Digital Tajamar*, 1-228.
- Severiche, C., Cabeza, M. R., Tovar, C. V., Rojas, D. M., & Hernández, Y. G. (2021). Marco legal regulatorio de la salud laboral para las cooperativas de recolectores de residuos sólidos urbanos. *Archivos Venezolanos de Farmacología y Terapéutica*, 40(8), 853-857.

- Severiche, C., Simanca, L. L. C., & Arnedo, J. T. M. (2023b). Políticas públicas ambientales para la salud laboral: Propuesta de un modelo en recolectores de residuos sólidos urbanos. *Criterio Libre*, 21(38), e259861-e259861.
- Severiche-Sierra, C., Barreto-Guerra, D., Puello-Martínez, A., Lugo-Calderon, E., & Ahumada-Villfañe, I. (2023c). Procedimiento de Salud Laboral en Cooperativas de Recicladores del Caribe Colombiano. *Revista Científica Profundidad Construyendo Futuro*, 18(18), 48-58.
- Torres-Rey, C, Conde-Sierra, J, Checa-Guerrero, D, Díaz-Criollo, S, Palma-Parra, R, & Varona-Uribe, M. (2012). Servicios de medicina del trabajo en Colombia. *Revista de Salud Pública*, 14(4), 598-606.
- Valero-Pacheco, I, & Riaño-Casallas, M. (2020). Teletrabajo: Gestión de la Seguridad y Salud en el Trabajo en Colombia. *Archivos de Prevención de Riesgos Laborales*, 23(1), 22-33.
- Vallejo, C. P. (2023). Impacto de la promoción de la salud en el trabajo, en la cultura preventiva de la Organización. *Gestión de la seguridad y la salud en el trabajo*, 5(1 (6)), 19-29.
- Vera Rubiano , O. A. ., & Molina Romero, J. (2023). Condiciones de la salud laboral bajo la resolución 3050 en Colombia . *Revista Colombiana De Salud Ocupacional*, 13(1), e-10165.
- Zapata Albán, M, Espinal, L, Marín, J, & Rodríguez, J. (2017). Calidad de vida en el trabajo en funcionarios del área de Seguridad y Vigilancia de una universidad del suroccidente colombiano. *Medicina y Seguridad del Trabajo*, 63(248), 235-244.